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GAMEHEARTS

Policy Brief 1

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Executive Summary

This first, five-chapter policy brief from the GAMEHEARTS project presents key findings from the project's first year and offers recommendations intended to benefit commercial, cultural, social, and policy-making stakeholders seeking to develop the potential of the European video games sector. The brief is structured as follows: after a short introduction in Chapter 1, Chapter 2 reports on GAMEHEARTS work that establishes and analyses the place that video games occupy in the lives of European citizenry. The chapter argues for expansion of video gaming into the wider cultural and creative sector of which it has by now become a vital part. Chapter 3 of the report provides a further contextualisation of the importance of the European video games industry by setting out the key features of the policy landscape within which it has evolved and operates. It provides an overview of commonalities and differences of approach and considers the further development of policies that might contribute to expanding and enhancing the growth of the European video games sector. Chapters 4 and 5 of the brief provide an analysis of how the expansion of the European video games sector might occur based on the evidence of research undertaken in the first year of GAMEHEARTS. Chapter 4 focuses on collaboration and between video games industry players and organisations and interests from the wider cultural and creative industries (CCI). It sets out the challenges and opportunities in growing collaboration between a range of people and organisations that have different resource capacities and motivations but share a common desire to explore opportunities for the expansion of video games into the wider creative and cultural sector. Chapter 5 builds on the theme of expansion through setting out GAMEHEARTS evidence on – and analysing – the untapped potential of video games in contributing to a more inclusive European society. The chapter focuses on video game players and reports specifically on GAMEHEARTS project work aimed at designing video games to cater for a greater diversity of players. The chapter argues this is not only culturally and socially significant, but can also present a commercial opportunity.

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About GAMEHEARTS

GAMEHEARTS is an innovative three-year EU and UK funded research project exploring the social and cultural value of the European video game industry. The project adopts an ecosystem approach that explores the role and contribution of key industry players and the numerous and varied actors within the wider video gaming sector.

The project explores the importance of the European video game industry ecosystem in contributing to economic growth, job creation, physical and mental wellbeing, and social and cultural cohesion. In particular, it seeks to locate and explore the relationships the gaming industry has within the wider cultural sector, and with other creative and cultural industries.

The project's consortium comprises nine key partners, across six different European countries. The academic partners are the universities of Salford (UK), Tampere (Finland), Vienna (Austria), Breda University of Applied Sciences (Netherlands), and Wroclaw University of Economics and Business (Poland). These organisations will work closely throughout all stages of the project with the project's lead industry partner, Ubisoft (France). GAMEHEARTS will also explore how video games intersect with other cultural industries, and how a closer working relationship between these traditional and emerging cultural industries may benefit all. In this respect, the project undertakes three case studies to understand better the location and role of video games in sport, visitor attractions, and live events, where GAMEHEARTS researchers will work in close partnership with the City Football Group (UK), Imperial War Museums (UK), and the London Symphony Orchestra (UK). However, the project has, from the planning stages through to its implementation and progression, sought to engage in an ongoing – and as wide as possible – dialogue with video game industry and other cultural sector representatives and organisations.

GAMEHEARTS is led and coordinated by the University of Vienna. The University of Salford steers the project's scientific direction and oversees the outputs and dissemination of the research. The project is organised in three key phases and seven work packages, each led by a different academic partner. The first phase of the project involved a series of workshops – one in each of the academic partner countries – as a way of engaging with industry and policy makers to get their initial input into the research and its direction. In the second phase of the project, Wroclaw University explores the business side of the game industry; the University of Vienna undertakes an examination of the key policy characteristics and opportunities of the

European games sector; and Tampere University and the University of Salford are researching how gamers use and connect with games. In phase three, Breda (in partnership with the University of Salford) will work with the project's cultural partners to build and test different experimental game environments to explore how games are, and could be, used to engage wider audiences.

The research undertaken in the GAMEHEARTS project is producing a series of key deliverables, of which this first project policy brief is a part. The work of the GAMEHEARTS project will culminate in a series of key policy and industry recommendations, that will seek to emphasise and maximise the value of the video games industry in the context of the creative and cultural sector and the wider European political-economic landscape.

Chapter 1. Introduction

This first policy brief from GAMEHEARTS presents work from the project's first year. It draws together the key findings from five deliverables produced in the project to date. Based on these reports, this policy brief offers recommendations intended to benefit commercial, cultural, social, and policy-making stakeholders seeking to develop further the potential of the European video games sector. The report is structured as follows.

Chapters 2 and 3 are context setting. Chapter 2 establishes and analyses the place that video games occupy in the lives of European citizenry. Notwithstanding some key challenges, it argues that there is potential for further expansion of video gaming into the wider cultural and creative sector of which it has by now become a vital part. The chapter also points to the work of key 'cultural intermediaries' – people and organisations outside of the immediate world of the gaming industry – that can use their 'social capital' (valuable social networks and connections) to promote the importance of video games. Chapter 3 of the report provides a further contextualisation of the importance of the European video games industry by setting out the key features of the policy landscape within which it has evolved and operates. The chapter analyses the ways in which the industry is governed and steered in Europe, drawing on the findings of our research from the case examples explored in the project. It provides an overview of commonalities and differences of approach and considers the scope for the further development of policies that might contribute to enhancing the growth of the European video games sector. Together, Chapters 2 and 3 of the brief establish a case for expanding the value and development of the European video games sector into the future.

Chapters 4 and 5 of the brief explore this potential in more detail. Chapter 4 sets out the character of collaboration between video games industry players and organisations and interests from the wider cultural and creative industries (CCI). Drawing on evidence gathered in the project to date, it shows the challenges and opportunities in growing collaboration between a range of people and organisations that have different resource capacities and motivations but share a common desire to explore opportunities for the expansion of video games into the wider creative and cultural sector. Chapter 5 of the brief builds on this core theme by taking a broader societal focus. It reports on GAMEHEARTS research that is exploring the untapped utility of video games in contributing to a more inclusive European society. Its particular focus is on video game players, a diverse group of people, many of whose preferences and requirements represent an opportunity for the development and growth of video games in Europe. The chapter reports specifically on GAMEHEARTS project work aimed at designing

games to cater for a greater diversity of audiences. The chapter argues that this is not only culturally and socially significant but also presents a potential commercial opportunity for the sector.

The evidence in this policy brief is based on the following GAMEHEARTS outputs:

- Bagnall, G., Crawford, G., Gislam, C., Gosling, V., Simpson, S., Stukoff, M, Yodovich, N. (2024). *Workshop Report*. Developed by the Horizon Europe project GAMEHEARTS (Games, Heritage, Arts, & Sport: the economic, social, and cultural value of the European video game ecosystem – GAMEHEARTS), funded by the European Union’s Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101132543, (106 pages).
- Klock, A. C. T., Hamari, J. (2024): *State-of-the-art Report: The Impact of Video Games in Shaping a More Inclusive Society*. Developed by the Horizon Europe project GAMEHEARTS (Games, Heritage, Arts, & Sport: the economic, social, and cultural value of the European video game ecosystem – GAMEHEARTS), funded by the European Union’s Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101132543, (35 pages).
- Kościewicz D., Klimas P., Strzelec G., Radomska J. (2025). *D3.1 State-of-the-art Report 1*. Developed by the Horizon Europe project GAMEHEARTS (Games, Heritage, Arts, & Sport: the economic, social, and cultural value of the European video game ecosystem – GAMEHEARTS), funded by the European Union’s Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101132543. (152 pages)
- Sarikakis, K., Gudkova, O., Alfonzo, L., Kartal, E., Winter L. (2024). *EU/Comparative Policy Report*. Developed by the Horizon Europe project GAMEHEARTS (Games, Heritage, Arts, & Sport: the economic, social, and cultural value of the European video game ecosystem – GAMEHEARTS), funded by the European Union’s Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101132543 (70 pages).
- Sundvik, Y; Sicevic, N; Ilesanmi, F. O.; Klock, A. C. T., Hamari, J. (2024): *Player-Centred Videogames Prototypes*. Developed by the Horizon Europe project GAMEHEARTS (Games, Heritage, Arts, & Sport: the economic, social, and cultural value of the European video game ecosystem – GAMEHEARTS), funded by the European Union’s Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101132543, (39 pages).

Chapter 2. Setting the Context: How Video Games are/are not valued

Introduction

According to annual data from Ipsos on the five largest European consumer markets (UK, France, Italy, Spain, and Germany), 53% of these populations play video games, and of these, 75% are adults. This report also states that 70% of 6-10 year-olds, and 83% of 11-14 year-olds regularly play video games (Video Game Europe, 2024). This pattern is replicated globally, with an estimated 3.2 billion regular players worldwide (Wijman, 2022). Notwithstanding these impressive statistics, it is nevertheless the case that the video games sector is still haunted by a lack of acceptance, by many, as an important and legitimate cultural form.

As video games continue to be omnipresent in our everyday cultural landscape, and as they continue to interact with other cultural fields, it is therefore crucial to understand the ways in which their cultural value and contribution are assessed, and their legitimisation is created. Thus, in this section, we consider their social and cultural value, explore pathways to the legitimisation of video games, and in particular the key role of external ‘cultural intermediaries’ here.

Our analysis of the cultural value and position of the games sector has been assisted in the GAMEHEARTS project by evidence gathered in a workshop conducted by project researchers at the University of Salford entitled *Video Games in/as Culture* (June 2024). This brought together experts from the worlds of journalism, broadcasting, video game development, curation, charitable organisations, and government bodies to discuss their experience of the cultural value of video games. The workshop comprised a keynote by TV and radio presenter Elle Osili-Wood, followed by two panel discussion sessions (see Bagnall *et al.*, 2024). The aim of this event was to:

- **Provide evidence of the position of video games, as and in culture.**
- **Explore the roles of ‘cultural intermediaries’ – individuals and organisations – that can and do support processes of cultural legitimisation of video games**

The evidence gathered here, and in the other activities of the initial stages of the GAMEHEARTS project, provides an essential basis on which to contextualise and understand the contribution of the GAMEHEARTS project to the future of the European video games industry.

How Video Games Matter

To call video games ‘valuable’ can have multiple meanings depending on the type of value being envisioned. Video games have for decades generated considerable revenue for studios and investors, as well as indirect revenue for connected businesses, individuals, and nation states. The game sector is also a major employer – for example, Video Games Europe suggests that, in 2023, the European game industry employed over 114,000 workers and that the value of this consumer market was over €25 billion (Video Games Europe, 2024).

These figures make a compelling argument that video games ‘matter’ economically. However, in recent years, the discussion of the importance of video games has broadened. This has at least four aspects to it:

- **First, it has been argued that playing video games can have psychological, health, and social benefits.** Examples include providing routes into reading for young people, aiding recovery from trauma for emergency service personnel, as well as warding off loneliness and promoting sport activities during the COVID-19 pandemic.
- **Second, gamification is important.** This is the argument that areas of social life that were once clearly demarcated as ‘not fun and games’, have increasingly drawn game-like elements into their practices. For example, gamification has transformed many traditionally non-playful domains like health and education by incorporating game-like features, such as the mental health app *Finch*, and the language learning platform *Duolingo*, which utilise experience points, streaks, and leaderboards to encourage user engagement.
- **Third, video games can have a positive impact towards development of skills and abilities.** This includes both directly how video game-based simulations are used in training in many different professions such as, corporate, healthcare, military and aviation training, to name but a few. But also, it has been suggested that playing certain video games can lead to improved multitasking, communication, resourcefulness, and adaptability skills, amongst others, in gamers.
- **Fourth, the video game industry has spilled over into other areas of economic and social life.** This is the argument that video game technologies have wider, and sometimes less obvious, applicability in many other industries and sectors. In fact, the video game industry is often the precursor of many technological developments. The automotive

industry, for example, uses the Unreal engine to streamline the car design process, as well as simulate dangerous scenarios such as animals running into the road. Similarly, architecture, engineering, and construction use game engines to plan buildings and visualise how space will be experienced with different lighting and building materials.

The Cultural Acceptance of Video Games

Shyon Baumann in his book *Hollywood Highbrow* (2007) argues that cinema gained cultural legitimacy due to three critical factors:

- First, an 'opportunity space' developed due to demographic and technological shifts, including a rise in university graduates and the advent of television as a competing medium.
- Second, key institutional developments occurred, such as the establishment of film festivals and academic programmes teaching film.
- Third, a narrative discourse emerged that recognised cinema as an art form.

It is similarly evident that **a demographic shift is taking place with video games**. The generation that played the first consoles and home computer games in the late 1970s and early 1980s are now middle-aged. Many have continued playing video games – alone or with their children – but even for those who have not, gaming has been part of the cultural landscape for most of their lives. For film, the rise of television significantly altered the perception of cinema by shifting audiences away from theatres, forcing Hollywood to differentiate itself from TV. As television became a dominant form of everyday entertainment, film studios focused on creating content seen as more prestigious, artistic, or intellectually engaging. Video games are yet to see a new technology that sits in the same cultural space as television did with film; however, other technological advances, most notably the rise of mobile devices, streaming services, and smart televisions, are impacting on the industry by helping to widen the opportunities to play video games.

In recent decades, we have also witnessed **the rise of academic study and cultural festivals focused on games**. Though Game Studies as an academic discipline is still some way behind more established subjects such as Film and Literary Studies, it is a rapidly growing area of study that trains the new generation of developers and contributes to the recognition of

the value of games. There is also **an increasing number of video game specific festivals and conventions**, including Koln Gamescom, Women in Games Festival, and the London Games Festival – to name but a few. These events differ in terms of their audiences and focus, as some target business (Paris Game Connection), industry professionals (Pocket Games), as well as consumer trade fairs (Gamescom). As such, these events may have different cultural purposes (some might seek cultural recognition, while others aim to expand video games' reach to broader audiences), but all highlight the increasing presence of video games in everyday life. We are also beginning to see **video games having a presence at other general cultural festivals**, such as at SXSW or the Tribeca Film Festival. This helps raise the cultural standing and visibility of video games. Game festivals, however, should not be seen as only catering to video games' existing audiences, for as highlighted by one of the panellists at *Video Games as/in Culture*, Michal French, Head of Games at Games London, at game festivals family groups will often attend with just one member who is a gamer. Hence, the organisers of festivals and events are important cultural intermediaries who play a key role in drawing in not just gamers, but also a wider audience. Moreover, game awards (like BAFTA) have become an essential platform for establishing games as an independent field of cultural production. These awards provide the video game industry events to celebrate games as cultural products in their own right.

It is also evident that **video games are increasingly being accepted alongside other cultural forms**, and certainly there is an argument that video games (or certain games, or aspects of games) might be considered as an art form. For example, in recent times we have also seen the development of several video game specific museums. Examples here include the Computerspielemuseum (Computer Games Museum) that opened in Berlin in 1997, Moscow's Museum of Soviet Arcade Machines in 2007, the UK's National Videogame Museum, which opened as the National Videogame Arcade in 2015, as well as the Nintendo Museum that opened in Kyoto in 2024. These examples are accompanied by the establishment of the EFGAMP, the European Federation of Game Archives Museums and Preservation Projects, in 2012 with the aim of preserving digital games and other interactive experiences. **This creation of public space specifically devoted to the history and cultural importance of video games furthers the argument for them being accepted as a legitimate medium** that belongs alongside other culturally significant artefacts. As Cat Powell (Director of Visitor Experience and co-CEO of the UK's National Videogame Museum) suggested during the

GAMEHEARTS Salford workshop, placing video games in a museum setting highlights their cultural value, and further opens games up to a wider audience, beyond those who typically play them.

However, it is not just museums specifically dedicated to video games that are now recognising gaming's cultural and historical value. Other more general museums and galleries now house video games as part of their permanent collections or have held specific video game exhibitions. For example, museums such as the Museum of Modern Art (MoMA) in New York have incorporated video games into their collections, recognising them as 'outstanding examples of interaction design'. In 2018, the Victoria and Albert Museum (V&A) in London put on an exhibition entitled *Videogames: Design/Play/Disrupt* that examined game designers' creative processes and video games' cultural impact. Another notable exhibition was the Imperial War Museum's (IWM) *War Games* that ran from the end of 2022 to mid-2023.

These exhibitions, and others, place video games alongside (physically and culturally) other key artefacts, such as significant works of art like the sculpture *Cybele* by Rodin (at the V&A, London), or historical items, like the fuselage of a Lancaster bomber (at IWM London), arguably one of the most important planes of the Second World War. Here, curators and museum professionals act as cultural intermediaries and have played a pivotal role in recontextualising video games within museum spaces, thereby providing them with cultural legitimacy. **Their expert framing of video games alongside other cultural forms therefore helps transform public perceptions of video games from mere entertainment to objects of design and heritage.**

Lastly, **cultural policy key players and stakeholders** have also played a significant role in establishing the value of video games as art. The state aid framework, championed by EGDF (European Games Developer Federation) since 2007 (beginning with France's first case), has played a crucial role in establishing games within cultural policy debates, by defining what qualifies video games as cultural products. Trade associations and NGOs have further reinforced this status, as no cultural field thrives without professional organisations. For example, groups like Women in Games, IGDA (International Game Developers Association), and EGDF each approach games as a cultural product from different perspectives.

Continued Challenges

The continued cultural acceptance of video games is not, however, without its controversies and challenges. For example, museums often must contend with the issue of the video games ‘playwall’ – as it was referred to at the Salford workshop by Elle Osili-Wood. Ian Kikuchi, Senior Curator of the IWMs’ *War Games* exhibition, spoke about the difficulty of bringing video games to public spaces such as museums. This is because interactive design has to be accessible to accommodate the diverse needs of museum visitors. There is, however, the argument that video games are ‘good’ for museums and galleries. For example, video games can help attract a new, often younger, audience into museums, and gamifying exhibitions can bring a more engaging and immersive experience for visitors. Additionally, virtual museums can be used to house exhibitions, or give experiences, that would not normally be possible in a physical museum. One example is the Pompeii exhibition at the Grand Palais in Paris in 2020, which offered a VR experience created by Ubisoft which allowed visitors to explore (virtually) a recently uncovered house and gardens in Pompeii in their current state, and also, how they would have been before the eruption of Vesuvius in 79AD. However, there are many critics who have questioned if video games should be included alongside (other) great works of art and historically significant artefacts. This includes, for example, *The Guardian* journalist and art critic, Jonathan Jones, who in 2012 railed against the inclusion of video games in the MoMA, arguing that they should not be there, because ‘video games are not art’.

The question of ‘are video games art?’ is one that has already been widely discussed by many others (such as, Bourgonjon *et al.*, 2017; Parker, 2018), but there are still at least two important points to make here:

- First, **the argument for video games as art is only usually applied to certain video games**, which typically includes the likes of *Journey*, *Disco Elysium*, and *Myst*. Certain – often very successful – video games, such as the *Call of Duty* series or *Candy Crush Saga* rarely (if ever) get considered as art – though they may include within them what might be deemed ‘artistic work’.
- Second, **internal arguments over the status of video games as art or not are unlikely to change wider perceptions of the medium**. Change will more likely come from cultural intermediaries, beyond the walls of game culture.

Hence, we argue that conflating the question ‘are video games art?’ with ‘are video games culturally valuable?’ distracts from identifying the process in which games are enveloped into a perceived cultural hierarchy. And that, internal debates within game culture over the status of video games as art or not, are unlikely to change wider perceptions of the medium, as change will more likely come from cultural intermediaries, beyond the walls of game culture.

The Continued Road to Cultural Legitimacy

Not everything in a gallery, and certainly not in a museum or at a cultural festival, needs to have been intentionally made to be ‘art’. Much that we now see as art was first and foremost initially made to amuse and entertain a wide range of audiences, such as, for example, the works of Shakespeare. Even the question of cinema as art is far from resolved (for example, see Abell, 2020). However, placing video games alongside other cultural artefacts, physically and symbolically, is important in generating discussion concerning their legitimate place within valued culture. **It is here again that cultural intermediaries play a crucial role in creating focus and discussion on video games.** For example, it is arts journalists and reviewers who play a crucial role in classifying and evaluating cultural products, including both traditional and emerging cultural forms. Examples here include, not just cinema, but also cases like nouvelle cuisine and pop music, where what played a key role in their cultural acceptance was **the power and influence of external cultural intermediaries**, who were central in legitimising these emerging cultures. Through the efforts of games journalists, who have pushed for moving video games from financial and tech pages to cultural pages, the gaming press has played a key role in establishing video games as an art form. However, **there are limits to what those working in the field of video games can do to secure cultural legitimacy.** It is the crossovers, and interactions, with more established cultural forms, such as museums, galleries, and others, like cinema, and the cultural intermediaries working in these domains, that possibly offer the most profitable route to the cultural acceptance of video games. One such case is how the award-winning film producer and director Eloise Singer chose to make a video game of *The Pirate Queen: A Forgotten Legend* (Singer Studios, 2024) instead of a film, and cast Lucy Liu in the titular role. As a panelist in the Salford GAMEHEARTS workshop, Singer spoke about using established film industry methods and networks to promote the game. Singer also took the game to film festivals, where it won awards at Tribeca and Raindance, as well as setting up press junkets with herself and Liu. By

engaging with the processes and institutions of an already legitimised medium, as well as their experts and celebrities, Singer played the role of a cultural intermediary, bringing her existing social and cultural capital to promoting her game.

Conclusion

This chapter has aimed to lay the foundations for further research which explores the questions of how and why video games matter. Some of the key points of the chapter are as follows:

- **Cultural Relevance:** Video games are an integral and growing part of contemporary culture, influencing and being influenced by other established cultural forms, such as film and television.
- **Economic and Cross-Sector Value:** Beyond their economic impact, video games contribute innovations and tools to industries such as education, healthcare, and design, showcasing their broader utility.
- **Legitimisation through Institutions:** The rise of academic disciplines, cultural festivals, and museums dedicated to or inclusive of video games demonstrates their gradual acceptance as valuable cultural artifacts.
- **Intersection with Art:** While debates continue about video games as art, they are increasingly viewed as creative works, with certain games recognised for their artistic or narrative qualities.
- **Role of Cultural Intermediaries:** Institutions, professionals, and events outside traditional gaming culture play a crucial role in reshaping perceptions and fostering the cultural legitimacy of video games.
- **Continued Challenges:** Despite progress, video games face hurdles in achieving the same cultural status as older media, requiring further connections into established cultural spaces and narratives.

Chapter 3. Setting the Context: the European Video Games Policy Landscape

Introduction

Chapter 2 of this policy brief highlighted the now widely established understanding of the cultural, economic, and social importance of video games in Europe. Video games have been growing in popularity for many years and are now an important part of the lives of Europeans of all ages. Yet, a core theme of this policy brief is the further potential for the sector to expand its resonance and value. The video games industry is technologically dynamic, exhibiting a constant drive to improve the quality of its products and services. It is also highly competitive, where companies seek innovative ways to market and monetise their products and services to an increasingly diverse consumer base. The growth of the European video games sector has focused the attention of policy makers on its current functioning and possible future development. Understanding the broad policy and regulatory environment within which the European video games industry has developed is crucial. This context sheds light on the measures taken to foster industry growth while safeguarding and promoting the interests of video games consumers. Establishing this context, in complement with Chapter 2, can allow us to think about ways in which the value of the video games industry can be enhanced and extended. The latter is the subject of Chapters 4 and 5 of this policy brief that focus, respectively, on collaboration between the video games industry and the wider cultural and creative sector; and the role that video games can play in creating a more inclusive society.

Researchers in the GAMEHEARTS team at the University of Vienna have undertaken an analysis of EU level and selected national policies for the games sector (see Sarikakis et al., 2024 – GAMEHEARTS deliverable D4.1). Methodologically, this research involved sourcing and documentary analysis of key primary source materials (legal texts, policy position papers and statements; regulatory pronouncements) and relevant secondary sources (press reports and academic analyses); alongside a series of semi-structured interviews and workshops with regulatory officials, policy makers, industry players, and academics.

Common Features of the European Video Games Policy Landscape

The analysis of the European video games policy landscape has revealed some shared policy goals that aim to:

- **protect consumer and player rights and welfare**
- **pursue sustainable industrial growth with concerns for the environment, cultural heritage, and social inclusion**
- **protect the creative and commercial freedoms and IP rights of game developers**
- **create and sustain the conditions for an open and competitive European digital market within which video gaming can take its place**
- **ensure a strong supply of new industry talent and expertise**
- **gain access to public support at national and EU levels**
- **recognise video games as creative and unique works**

There is evidence of a broad shared understanding among commercial and policy making stakeholders of the importance of:

- **providing content to consumers in an age appropriate fashion**
- **ensuring fairness and transparency in the monetisation of game products**
- **establishing safe and healthy game environments for all players**
- **addressing opportunities arising from the opening up of the video games data and distribution value chain**
- **protecting and appropriately using the data of video game consumers**
- **fostering the development of video gaming talent and expertise**
- **supporting the growth of small and larger video game companies as part of a strategy of cultural and economic development**

Policy measures in place often involve a combination of at least some of the following:

- **the use of legislative (legal) measures related to consumer protection (including product safety); data protection and privacy, Intellectual Property, and platform regulation**
- **the use of internationally developed voluntary self-regulatory industry standards**
- **an expectation of significant user self-regulation (through individuals taking responsibility, education, and parental guardianship)**
- **significant – though – variable state support for the video games sector**

Yet, at the same time, it is important to note that the European video games policy landscape is heterogeneous with diverse approaches at the national level regarding efforts to ensure industrial development, consumer protection, and broader social responsibility (for more details, see: Sarikakis et al., 2024 – GAMEHEARTS deliverable D4.1). The European Union has become a significant policy actor in the European video games environment through the provision of a number of important generic legislative measures with direct applicability to video games. A key part of the EU's digital strategy is the goal of promoting sectoral innovation alongside effective and appropriate regulation (Borgese, 2023). The importance of the video game industry to the EU's cultural and digital economy is becoming increasingly apparent. Ensuring the protection of European video gamers' data has been significantly assisted by the EU's General Data Protection Regulation, in particular regarding data use and the provision of targeted advertising towards minors, EU Consumer Protection Regulation and newer regulation such as the Digital Services Act. The EU has sought to balance intellectual property protection with preserving and promoting cultural diversity 'to facilitate cultural exchange within its borders while preventing cultural homogenisation' (Sarikakis et al., 2024: 13 – GAMEHEARTS deliverable D4.1).

Key video game regulatory policy matters in Europe

There is a growing understanding of the importance of an appropriate legal and regulatory framework to allow the development and functioning of the European video games sector for industry actors and consumers alike. GAMEHEARTS researchers at the University of Vienna have explored the following key issues: content regulation and age classification; consumer protection; data protection and privacy; environmental sustainability; diversity; and measures to promote video game industry development.

Content Regulation and Age Classification

Industry self-regulation through professional standards setting is one of the most important and successful aspects of the governance of the European video games sector. The Pan European Games Information (PEGI) system (Robertson, 2008) aims to facilitate safer gaming conditions for players, especially minors, and the promotion of consumer trust in the video games sector. The PEGI system is run through PEGI SA, an independent, private, not-for-profit

organisation established under Belgian law. It has been adopted in 40 European countries by 2600 members companies and has classified as many as 40,000 video games. Through a self-regulatory system, PEGI assigns age ratings and content labels to video games and ‘addresses concerns related to in-game purchases’, (Sarikakis et al., 2024: 13 – GAMEHEARTS deliverable D4.1) PEGI’s significance has been recognised by a variety of parties, from EU policy makers and national legislators, to major video game console makers, and further to parents and guardians of minors (Video Games Europe, 2023). PEGI provides an important example of the role that effective industry self-regulation can play in the evolution of the European video games sector. It provides an indication of the ability of the video games sector to self-organise and self-manage and suggests the potential for further developments of this kind in new directions to sustain and grow the industry into the future.

This notwithstanding, GAMEHEARTS researchers at the University of Vienna have found that the enforcement of PEGI varies at the national level across Europe, particularly in physical retail. This ‘challenges game developers as they navigate compliance with national regulations while striving to protect minors through responsible content ratings’ (Sarikakis et al., 2024: 15 – GAMEHEARTS deliverable D4.1). A debate has occurred on the extent to which game developers, on the one hand, and gaming platforms, on the other, should have responsibility for content rating compliance with academic research suggesting that this should be a shared, collaborative responsibility (Singh and Rizvi, 2023) of which PEGI provides an important example.

Consumer Protection

GAMEHEARTS researchers at the University of Vienna have found considerable variety in national approaches to consumer protection in the video games sector. Some states, such as Finland, Belgium, and the Netherlands, focus on transparency and fair-trade practices in consumer protection law with detailed information required in the areas of in-game purchases and refund policies. Other states, such as Austria, France, Italy, and Spain, show evidence of a narrower approach related to refund rights without a focus on the broader issue of transparency (for more details, see Sarikakis et al., 2024 – GAMEHEARTS deliverable D4.1). As video gaming continues to grow in importance and become more closely aligned with other aspects of the digital world, regulatory concern about consumer rights will remain very important.

There is evidence of a complex relationship between the revenue models of video gaming companies, consumer protection, and approaches to regulation of video games across Europe and globally, exemplified by the current debate over loot boxes, where there is evidence of the development of a largely (though not exclusively) similar approach to loot box regulation, viewed as a matter of consumer protection. Empirical work conducted by GAMEHEARTS researchers at the University of Vienna has found that video game ‘industry experts advocate for a balanced stance...suggesting measures like age restrictions and spending limits’ (Sarikakis et al., 2024: 17 – GAMEHEARTS deliverable D4.1). There is evidence of concern from the industry about the over-regulation of purchases of in-game content (at storefront level) that could negatively impact the development of the mobile games industry, slow innovation, and ultimately undermine the economic contribution that video games can make in the future (Lee and Schiller, 2019). It is the case that ‘finding a balance between protecting consumers and maintaining a thriving digital economy remains a complex challenge for policy makers and the gaming industry’ (Sarikakis et al., 2024: 19-20 – GAMEHEARTS deliverable 4.1).

Self- and co- regulation in video games allows the provision of advice to parents and players to ensure that video game experiences are fair and responsible in character. A self- and co-regulatory structure has the flexibility and responsiveness to address consumer concerns quickly compared to legislation making. EU Consumer Law Guidance has added the self- and co-regulatory transparency requirements provided by PEGI and the European Parliament (2020) has highlighted the efforts that have been made by the video games industry to structure loot boxes to minimise harm to young audiences. VIDEOGAMES EUROPE and the European Games Developer Federation (2024) have found that around 4 % of players of all ages engage with loot boxes and around 11% of video games players engage with in-game currencies. Among those children that are allowed by their parents to purchase content to use in game, 95 % of parents supervise their child’s activity.

Data Protection and Privacy

The importance of protecting gamers’ data is universally recognised in the sector and provides another baseline indicator of the amenability of video games industry players to adopt socially responsible practices. This is particularly important given the highly engaging nature of some video games, which can expose minors, in particular, to data privacy risks (Stoilova et al.,

2021). Whilst the EU's GDPR provides an important framework for data protection applied to the video games sector, GAMEHEARTS researchers found evidence of a variety of regulatory practices regarding its enforcement at the national level (for more details, see Sarikakis et al., 2024 – GAMEHEARTS deliverable D4.1).

Environmental Sustainability

There is a growing recognition of the importance of ensuring that the video games industry considers its environmental impact and pursues a path of environmentally sustainable development and growth in the future. The Sustainable Games Alliance, a nonprofit organisation, has produced a live, iteratively developing standard with the minimum goal of helping its members meet legal obligations under mandatory disclosure legislation, such as the EU Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive. The Standard provides members with 'guidance, definitions, data, documents and tools' (Sustainable Games Alliance, 2025) and is another significant example of video games industry self-organisation to address contemporary challenges. In the Netherlands, work has been undertaken in the STRATEGIES project with the dual aim of reducing environmental harm from the development, distribution, and consumption of video games, as well to use video games content to promote awareness of environmental matters among video game players (Gameresearch, 2024).

Diversity

In Europe, in 2023, 24.4 % of the videogame workforce was made up of women, comparing favourably with the film production sector (24% in 2023) (European Audiovisual Observatory, 2024) and the information and communication technologies sector as a whole (19,4% in 2023) (Eurostat 2024).

There is significant evidence of policy measures aimed at the protection and promotion of diversity in the European video games industry, though there is an opportunity to develop this into the future in a more intensive and systematic fashion. For example, Austria's Federal Act on Equal Treatment prohibits discriminatory practice in the video game industry regarding content production and employment. The UK games workforce has a higher-than-average proportion of LGBTQ+ and neurodiverse employees, with a growing number of women and

gender non-binary people working in it (UK Games Industry Census 2022). Finland's Non-Discrimination and Equality Act (2024) prohibits discrimination on grounds of age, gender, disability, ethnicity, and sexual orientation and requires video game companies to create a culture of inclusivity in their employed workforce and game content. In Poland, the GameINN project (launched by the National Centre for Research and Development) has a focus on promoting diversity in game character development, cultural diversity, and inclusivity in video game mechanics.

There is a growing recognition within the video games industry that a diverse workforce is a necessary condition for developing a culture in which game content reflects the wide range of cultural experiences and preferences of society at large. Diversity is also a matter under the scope of the EU Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive. A diverse workforce can be regarded as a necessary condition to achieve diversity in content because video games companies can use not just the technical expertise of their workforce but also harness the life experiences and cultural preferences of that workforce in the production of gaming content. Moving in this direction has the potential to develop the commercial reach of the industry in new directions.

Measures to Promote Video Game Industry Development

Public Support Measures for the Video Games Industry

There is significant evidence of direct and indirect public support measures for the video game sector (Sarikakis et al., 2024 – GAMEHEARTS deliverable D4.1). This is important in helping the video games industry become, on the one hand, more cohesive and expansive through collaborations, and, on the other, developing video games in new socially progressive and commercially lucrative directions. For example, Poland's GameINN initiative provides financial support for innovation in game development. Elsewhere, for example in the UK, there is evidence of tax support measures and opportunities to gain resources through creative industry grant schemes.

However, the funding environment for games development is fragmented and heterogeneous across Europe. This heterogeneity has nevertheless displayed the value and vitality of a range of measures in operation, such as cultural production support for content creation, R&D

support for games technology development and support to create video game industry start-up companies. Securing funding between pre-production and creating a demo or ‘vertical slice’ was found to be particularly challenging, a phase necessary to successfully attracting games publishers. Here ‘inconsistency and lack of cohesion present further hurdles for game studios trying to navigate the industry’s financial landscape’ (Sarikakis et al. 2024: 47 – GAMEHEARTS deliverable D4.1). The GAMEHEARTS team at the University of Vienna have unearthed evidence that suggests that a lack of collaborative financial models is significant and may be inhibiting the growth of collaboration between European gaming studios. They suggest that a focus on fewer, larger collaborative projects located beyond the R&D stage and closer to the market could also prove beneficial (Sarikakis et al. 2024: 47 – GAMEHEARTS deliverable D4.1) though any moves in this direction would need to take close consideration of EU competition policy. The European Investment Fund has become a new significant instrument in assisting the video games industry as exemplified by the recent award of Euro 20 million to a new Swedish initiative (European Investment Fund, 2025).

A European innovation model could be developed by the EU to facilitate revenue and IP sharing between commercial partners providing support for joint ventures to share readily resources and expertise between collaborators.

Developing the Video Games Labour Force

Some evidence suggests a degree of imbalance in the video games industry labour force with a shortfall in demand at entry level and under-supply at the level of experienced senior talent. It is important for universities and educational providers of vocational programmes to be aware of the need to develop better their offering as industry needs change. The research found niche, under-served areas that university curricula development could consider addressing such as AI, server-side technologies and monetisation strategies. **There is a need for a range of support measures to attract talent by simplifying visa processes, offering competitive compensation packages, and promoting Europe as an innovative hub for game development** which ‘could be achieved in part through EU-wide programmes or initiatives aimed at making Europe more competitive against other gaming markets’ (Sarakakis et al. 2024: 48).

Recommendations

The work of the GAMEHEARTS team at the University of Vienna has shown the importance of the European video games policy landscape. This can be developed further in the following ways:

- **Support early-stage European video game developers** with targeted financial assistance. This can involve measures such as grants and low-interest loans for cultural game production and the growth of new video games start ups. It can also involve state aid measures to stimulate R&D in the video games sector.
- **Support and enhance the development of the European video games workforce through education and training to grow and sustain a strong EU video gaming talent pool.**
- **Move towards a uniform framework for regulating loot boxes** in Europe. The current approach makes compliance challenging for games developers and a more uniform treatment under a consumer protection umbrella would create a better context for, on the one hand, the development of monetisation practices and, on the other, protection of video games consumers, particularly minors. There is evidence that industry players have advocated for clarity regarding age restrictions, player spending caps, and compulsory notifications of in-game expenditure and have taken significant steps to ensure transparency and consumer protection (Video Games Europe and European Games Developer Federation, 2024). Creating consistent standards can show Europe as a leader in socially responsible gaming with the potential to ensure further expansion of the industry to new video games consumers.
- **Enhance inclusivity and diversity in the European video games industry.** The European video games industry has significant potential to advance inclusivity and diversity within its quarters. This could be achieved through targeted training programmes focused on gender equality, variety and inclusivity, and cultural awareness, as well as increased focus on creating work environments that nurture and amplify diverse voices. This should be viewed as an opportunity for the European video games industry to grow its customer base because innovating through diverse and socially responsible game design can strengthen industry competitiveness and grow new markets.
- **Develop approaches to digital literacy, youth protection, and engaging younger generations**

In addition to the protective measures related to minors referred to elsewhere in this chapter (age labelling; loot box regulation), there could be further development of game design interfaces to emphasise features that educate children about personal welfare and security online building on examples such as Ubisoft's Good Game Playbook and Fair Play Program. This could be accompanied by the rollout of industry association safe gaming practice campaigns. This can complement parental guidance to children on safe and resilient digital practices. Video game education could be incorporated in schools into responsible participation in digital spaces education. It is important, through discussion with game developers, to explore where it might be possible to ensure that voices and preferences of young people are heard and included in video game development.

Chapter 4. Expanding the Video Games Industry Ecosystem: Collaborations with the Wider Cultural and Creative Industries

Introduction

A key aspect of the GAMEHEARTS project is an exploration of the current level of – and potential for further – collaboration between the European video game industry and the wider creative and cultural industries (CCI). This chapter of our policy brief sets out the work undertaken in the project that explores such collaboration and makes recommendations for increasing the quality and quantity of European video games industry–CCI partnerships at the level of policy. The chapter takes as its focus the research undertaken by the GAMEHEARTS team at Wrocław, as well as, where relevant, the findings from the series of stakeholder workshops conducted by GAMEHEARTS university partners between April and June 2024.

The increasing complexity of video game development often goes beyond the scope of what an individual game studio can achieve, subsequently incentivising intra-industry collaboration. A high-profile example is Kojima Productions, which partnered with Guerrilla Games to deploy and develop further its Decima engine for *Death Stranding* (2019) (Renardson, 2017). Such collaboration within the video games industry exemplifies the established capabilities of the industry to engage in partnerships as a method in which innovation can be achieved effectively and efficiently. From the perspective of the wider CCI, partnership with the video game industry brings with it access to these technological innovations and a sought-after expertise in the digital. Collaboration with the video games industry can draw in new audiences (Camps-Ortueta et al, 2021) as well as reimagine how the sectors can co-exist harmoniously (Muriel and Crawford, 2018). Some of the potential benefits for game studios that engage with CCI are discussed in GAMEHEARTS deliverable 2.2 *workshop report*. Video games industry–CCI partnerships can bring in vital funding and extend the value of video games beyond their typical audience. Meanwhile, evidence gathered in the project from workshops conducted at Breda University of Applied Sciences, Tampere University, and Wrocław University of Economics and Business demonstrates that this reward should be balanced alongside the risk entailed in engaging in a partnership.

Co-creating value from European Video Games Industry/CCI Collaboration

The preliminary findings of the project regarding cross-industry cooperation come from various sources such as: stakeholder workshops, industry reports, and academic literature review undertaken by the Wrocław team (see GAMEHEARTS deliverable 3.1. State-of-the-art report), as well as some preliminary quantitative data analysis presented at Poznań Game Arena 2024. Those preliminary findings are as follows:

- European video game studios, especially those of smaller scale, depend heavily on government aid, for example the UK Games Fund, in addition to other forms of public support. **Ongoing availability of access to funding on a local, national, and international level is vital for the dynamism of the industry.**
- A review of industry reports (detailed in Deliverable 3.1) found there is much diversity (as well as competition) between national video games markets with minimal cooperation. Such a multiplicity of approaches between national markets results in challenges in developing European wide policy and recommendations on how to nurture partnerships with the wider CCI. **Strategies to overcome this barrier should be considered by policy makers at the EU level, as well as games industry players.**

Current literature tends to focus on CCI such as film, TV, music, sports and live events, and museums. **Further research is needed on the nature of collaboration between games industry players and other parts of the CCI beyond these sectors such as publishing, architecture, theatre, and crafts. There is currently no academic study which seeks to understand the reasons behind the breakdown of partnerships which sometimes occurs between games industry players and wider CCI members. This is a gap in knowledge that needs to be closed as a priority.**

GAMEHEARTS Project Evidence of Collaboration Between Games Industry Players and Other Parties from the Cultural and Creative Sector

GAMEHEARTS researchers at Wrocław University of Economics and Business have undertaken stakeholder workshops (focusing on the CCI, including the video games industry), in-depth interviews (the first wave focusing on the video games industry, the second wave focusing on the CCI), and survey research (focusing on VGD registered in Europe) to understand better

current perspectives on, and experiences and outcomes of, collaboration between the CCI and the video games industry. This research is ongoing at the time of writing and full findings will be available in GAMEHEARTS deliverable 3.3, *Report & Recommendations for VGD*, set for publication at the end of 2025. The majority of raw data is currently under analysis, but preliminary findings suggest the following:

- Cooperation inside the European video games industry can be found in every stage of partnerships where co-innovation occurs, from the process of idea generation to post-launch activities and monitoring of market uptake and competitor reactions. However, cooperation at the points of creation, delivery, and dissemination are most common.
- Self-evaluation of organisational innovativeness by research participants suggests most value is placed on the dimension related to people, with product innovativeness in second place, and process innovativeness placed third. This suggests that the core dimension of video game developers' innovativeness is related to creative workers and management staff.
- Regarding the types of innovations adopted by the EGDF in their reports (2018), preliminary findings indicate that, in the perception of the surveyed video game developers, content innovations are rated most important in their organisations. Technological innovations rank second, followed by business innovations in third place.
- Evidence suggests that collaborative partnerships fail mainly due to:
 - financial constraints
 - legal constraints
 - misperceptions surrounding expectations, timings, and the value and importance of European Video games industry
 - a 'silo' mentality (tunnel vision which causes a focus only on one industry).
 - difficulty predicting factors that determine the success or failure of the game produced
 - Poor understanding of market-based conditions for the product of the collaboration.

Recommendations

Preliminary findings from the research conducted by GAMEHEARTS researchers at Wrocław University of Economics and Business lead to the following recommendations:

- Financial incentives/impediments are key factors for stakeholders from both the European video games industry and the wider CCI in considering whether to engage in collaboration. **European video games industry policy that aims to increase cross-industry partnerships should consider the creation of measures that reduce the cost of collaboration where connection to wider CCI partners will enhance the quality, reach, or otherwise benefit the proposed game.**
- Smaller scale video game developers rely on multiple initiatives on a local, national, and international level to secure funding for their work. **Policy makers should take measures to ensure that funding application processes are harmonised to ease the challenges that negotiating this complex and time-consuming funding landscape pose for the European video games industry and wider CCI players. These measures should balance creating a funding scheme which is equally supportive across Europe while avoiding the production of a standardised European funding model in order to preserve the innovation which occurs at the national level.**
- Video games industry and wider CCI players show evidence of holding different aspirations from potential collaboration. The European video games industry is most often comprised of companies that are profit driven, whereas other CCI organisations receive different funding and financial support where that funding is earmarked for cultural and broader societal goals. **Policy makers in designing funding that aims to encourage cross-industry partnership should recognise this diversity of aspiration and address it in the substance of funding calls produced.** Policy makers should consult more extensively with wider CCI players in designing such initiatives.
- **Policy makers should design better online systems to provide comprehensive and regularly updated information on funding opportunities.** This should include the creation of a series of accessible ‘advice resources’ for potential collaborators of all sizes hailing from both the European video games industry and the wider CCI sector to reduce opportunity search costs and increase the quality of applications produced ultimately.

- While the benefit of cooperation is generally understood, the process of starting a partnership can be daunting and/or difficult to achieve without specific connections and pre-established relationships. **Efforts should be made by funders to create collaboration networking opportunities focused on producing collaborative projects between the European video games industry and the wider CCI.** These events should occur both face-to-face and virtually to lessen barriers to entry, maximise engagement and moderate environmental externalities of participation across Europe. In addition, there is a knowledge gap regarding why initial collaboration is hindered beyond financial constraints. Efforts should be made in academia to assist industry by closing this gap.
- Redundancies; talent leakages to other sectors; the increasing adoption of video games as a site of cultural conflict; increases in the cost of creating video games; the pace of growth in the industry levelling after the boom produced by the COVID-19 lockdowns; as well as reduction in consumer demand due to the recent and current high inflation rates, are all significant challenges facing the games sector. Addressing these pressing problems can understandably narrow the focus of industry players on the games sector alone, at the expense of potentially fruitful collaborations with other sectors. **Policy makers should compensate for this by taking measures to promote and incentivise collaboration between European video games industry and wider CCI parties in the current highly challenging financial environment faced by these players.** These measures could include a general increase in the amount of funding offered, as well as tax relief incentives such as those that benefit the film and television industries and are currently only offered to the video games industry by France, Germany, Italy, and the UK. It should be noted that the European video game industry is at the forefront of innovation in the cultural and creative sectors, artistically, technologically and in terms of business strategy. These characteristics that help distinguish Europe's video game industry as world leading, are also in need of financial and policy orientated aid. Although there are many benefits to collaboration between EVGIE and other CCIs, it should also be acknowledged that any action taken to increase collaboration involves a potentially risky reallocation of resources from industry specific activity into a shared cross-industry endeavour.

Chapter 5. Expanding the Video Games Industry Ecosystem: Video Games for a More Inclusive Society

Introduction

The policy brief to this point has focused its attention on the video games industry as a whole. In our final chapter, we delve deeper by focusing on video games themselves, and the ways in which they might contribute to a more inclusive society. The growing integration of video games into society and the gamification of everyday life has begun to be explored in detail, with some research focusing on their potential to promote social inclusion (Bleumers, 2012; Hamari, 2019; Tomé Klock, 2024; YEU,2021). Yet the extent to which video games can drive social change, and how game design itself can become more inclusive, are poorly understood. A comprehensive examination of existing and potential gamification strategies for promoting inclusion (in game mechanics, as well as using games' audiovisual and narrative content to promote inclusion in wider society) is needed to guide future research and development and policy activity. As part of this endeavour, GAMEHEARTS researchers at Tampere University initiated two projects:

- **a state-of-the-art review of literature on inclusion and gamification;**
- **production of a player-centred video game prototype that aims to promote inclusion among marginalised young people.**

State-of-the-art of gamified EDI tools

GAMEHEARTS researchers at Tampere University assessed the current intersections between social inclusion and gamification, emphasising how video games can promote equity, diversity, and inclusion (EDI) in society. The team focused on three core issues: design (understanding context), development (understanding methods), and evaluation (understanding effects). The review identified two main research areas:

- **utilising gamification to foster EDI**
- **making gamification itself more inclusive.**

Existing academic work emphasises ways in which gamification can cultivate EDI in relation to marginalised groups such as women, children, the elderly, and immigrants (Casey, et al.,

2023; Hightow-Weidman, et al., 2021; Huang & Lau, 2020). Research has applied gamified strategies in fields like Science Technology, Engineering and Medicine (STEM) education (supporting parents as role models for children who had limited or no exposure to STEM disciplines); linguistic equity (helping refugee children learn mathematics in their native languages); and sexual health (promoting safe practices in venues associated with sexual activities).

In the second research area, academic work has focused on the specific topic of making gamification more inclusive by designing experiences attuned to a variety of demographics. This work seeks to align game design more closely with the needs and preferences of diverse groups, particularly those with historically limited access to technology and video games. These included gender-specific gamified tools for women learning mathematics, apps for older adults learning computer skills, and games addressing accessibility needs among people with disabilities in mathematics education. Overall:

- **education was found as the dominant field where gamification and inclusion often intersect, with gamified tools usually applied to improve mathematical skills and digital literacy.**
- **health was also found to be an area that utilised gamification for purposes such as sexual health or preventing substance abuse among marginalised individuals.**

Such gamified approaches predominantly relied on achievement-based game mechanics such as points, badges, and leaderboards. These elements collectively motivated users to engage and improve, regardless of the specific context, whether it was education, health, or civic engagement.

- **Nearly all academic work analysed psychological outcomes, with a focus on matters such as experience, motivation, anxiety, flow, and enjoyment.**
- **The outcomes of the research undertaken showed variance in the ability to promote inclusion through gamification.**

For instance, improved user experience was noted in educational settings among students and older adults. At the same time, gamified elements that reinforced gendered stereotypes, such as gendered interfaces (blue for men, purple for women), (cis)gender-based avatars and gender-based leaderboards (showing only “male” and “female” names), heightened

anxiety among women and impacted their motivation to learn maths. Moreover, while some studies noted improved user experience overall, others showed participation disparities based on age, with older adults expressing a lesser interest in engaging with gamified platforms.

Thus, the analysis of existing literature by the GAMEHEARTS team at Tampere University identified the following strengths and limitations in current gamified approaches to EDI:

- **Gamification has made significant strides in addressing gaps in STEM education and improving healthcare for marginalised groups.**
- **The interaction between gamification and EDI produced complex results:** while some groups experienced higher engagement and reduced effort, others found gamified elements unimpactful or even burdensome.
- **Most gamified EDI studies focus on achievement elements, while social and immersive game mechanics, which are considered vital for EDI, according to Tampere, were often under-represented in existing research.**

Player-centred video game prototype

As the Tampere team began developing their player-centred video game prototype, three relevant insights from the literature review conducted were drawn upon:

- **the potential of gamification to promote inclusion**
- **the increasing emphasis on gamification among children and young people**
- **the need for games that move beyond competition**

In producing its prototype, the team was led by the Positive Youth Development (PYD) framework (Lerner et al., 2005; Lerner, 2009), which highlights five key qualities: Competence, Confidence, Connection, Character, and Caring (also known as “the 5 C’s”). With this in mind, the team’s goal was to create a hybrid game, combining digital elements and real-world interaction, using the PYD framework and the “5 C’s”, to promote and nurture skills essential for self-development and inclusion among marginalised youth.

The design process comprised three stages:

- 1. needs assessment to align the game with youth requirements,**
- 2. a workshop with game designers to brainstorm concepts and narratives**
- 3. a design workshop with the Gamification Group's research team to refine the game's storyline and mechanics.**

In the first stage, and to ensure relevance to the target audience, the team collaborated with a Helsinki youth centre focusing on young people aged 15 to 25. The centre's activities are open to young people from diverse backgrounds, in terms of gender, sexuality, and neurodiversity. The centre is motivated to bring young people together, decrease loneliness, support youth employment and opportunities for education, and enhance media literacy skills. Key challenges were identified through conversations with the youth workers, such as disparities in gaming skills, language barriers, and technical proficiency.

The second stage, a design workshop, was held in October 2024. Here, a game concept that aligned with the needs identified at the youth centre was chosen. Space was found as a suitable theme as it reflected the experience of navigating the unknown and called for unity to achieve a common goal. In a follow-up workshop with the Gamification Group, the narrative was expanded, and key traits and characteristics of the protagonist were decided upon. It was established that the protagonist (in the game) should be lonely and uncertain, as well as determined, intriguing, social and friendly, thus reflecting qualities that resonate with a young audience.

Ultimately, the character of Xeno was conceived. Xeno is a space explorer with a morphing body on a mission to save their species. Xeno is sent on an exploration mission by the planet's research centre to discover a new natural resource that could save their species from impending extinction. The mission unfortunately fails, and Xeno returns to their home planet to deliver the news. Upon returning to their planet, Xeno finds it abandoned, hearing only a strange noise from a research capsule. This noise leads Xeno to discover a human (the young player in the youth centre) with whom they will have to interact and collaborate in order to survive, sparking a journey of connection, exploration, and mutual support.

Following the PYD framework, each segment of the game storyline connects to one of the 5 C's, guiding players in activities that foster these qualities. For example, players might need to demonstrate confidence by solving challenges with other players in real life, seeing their actions reflected in the digital realm. Each completed segment awards a specific "C," with the game requiring players to collect all five to succeed. This interactive design allows participants to develop these attributes while collaborating with others.

In the next phase of the GAMEHEARTS project, Tampere researchers will organise a collaborative workshop involving young people, youth workers, game developers, and other relevant stakeholders to ensure the game is inclusive and addresses specific needs effectively. The workshops will shape a detailed gameplay experience that mirrors both real-life interactions and digital feedback, providing a meaningful space for social inclusion and development.

Recommendations

- While promising, the current body of gamification and EDI research is far from exhaustive in academia and the video game industry as a whole. Interdisciplinary approaches are essential for its evolution. **Collaborative research efforts should be made across academia, industry, and policy makers as a step forward to ensure gamification contributes meaningfully to a more inclusive and socially sustainable society.**
- **Corporate sustainability reporting should highlight video game companies' efforts to promote inclusion and diversity.** These reports should also acknowledge that different game mechanics might affect individuals in varying ways, potentially fostering or hindering inclusion.
- **Guidelines for creating gamified platforms (such as ones using game mechanics for educational purposes, as described above) should be developed through collaborative discussions between industry and academia to consider the varying needs across age, gender, and disability.**
- **Guidelines should prioritise inclusivity in game mechanics, ensuring accessibility for players with diverse backgrounds and varying levels of gaming experience.**

- **Partnership between researchers, developers, and policy makers, such as the Sustainable Games Alliance, should be supported and promoted.** Such collaborations can create gamification guidelines that align with EDI objectives that could be adapted and adopted by the video games industry according to their needs and strategy to promote a more inclusive society.

Chapter 6. Conclusion

This policy brief has provided an outline of the core findings of the first year of the GAMEHEARTS project. The work of the project thus far has been foundation and context setting, as well as explorational. The latter will continue through the remainder of the project driven by the goal of establishing a case for expanding the development and value of the European video games sector into the future. This policy brief provides evidence affirming the increasingly recognised and important place that video games have in Europe's economic, commercial, cultural and societal landscape. Yet it also provides evidence of the potential to extend the value of video games into the wider cultural and creative sector. Whilst challenging, research conducted to date in the project points to the opportunity to achieve this, in the process acknowledging the video games sector as a strategically important part of Europe's digital economy. This policy brief - based on a set of key deliverables produced by the GAMEHEARTS team thus far - provides a rationale for supportive policies and cross-sector engagement to realise fully the potential of video games in Europe.

The next phase of the project, which builds on the findings of this report and other GAMEHEART deliverables, will focus on Video Games Industry-Cultural and Creative Industries (VGI-CCI) sector partnerships and collaborations more deeply. The University of Salford and Breda University of Applied Sciences will continue their work with our project cultural partners (London Symphony Orchestra, Imperial War Museum, and City Football Group), while Tampere University will continue to develop a video game with the purpose of cultivating inclusions and cooperation among young people. Wroclaw University of Economics and Business will hold events (DTthons) to bring people from the VGI and CCI together to engage with one another, while the University of Vienna will continue to examine the governance, policy and regulatory frameworks that can facilitate the video game industry to thrive and grow. The outcomes of the next phase of the project will culminate in a second policy brief, scheduled for publication at the end of 2026, that will provide findings and further detailed policy recommendations based on the research conducted in the remainder of the GAMEHEARTS project.

We conclude this report by highlighting that GAMEHEARTS is a collaborative effort between industry and academia. It is structured and functions as a co-productive conversation between academia, cultural organisations, industry, and policy-makers. In this spirit

and with this modus operandi, we invite readers to engage with GAMEHEARTS going forward so that we can continue to shape a more innovative and inclusive future for the European video games sector.

Comments and Feedback

Let's start a conversation about the future of the European video games sector. Please send comments on this policy brief to our project email:

info@gamehearts.eu

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